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Individual Paper

Modern models institutionalization of educational and problems and tasks of analysis of global transformations for social development at all levels

Basic Information

Subtitle:

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Submitter

Viktor Zinchenko

Content

Abstract:

The study of the general multicultural contexts of social development makes it clear that the invention of a new type of social development should become a priority area of social institutionalization. Institutionalized civil society is a socio-cultural factor, which includes the attitude of the person to the means not only of material production, but also of one's self-production as a social, cultural being.

The idea of civil society expresses a historical tendency to move to freedom from political and economic determinism, whereby a person becomes a co-owner of the universal conditions of his or her personal development, regardless of his / her socio-economic functions and roles.

Modern models of institutionalization and self-organization of social systems should be built on the basic foundations: intellectual and moral education, civic institutionalization, socially significant models of social management. For modern scientific thought, social studies and socio-philosophical, economic and political and management theories, the integration of developed societies in the modern «neo-capitalist» (or «neo-industrial», «post-industrial», «late-capitalist», according to other lexicon) stage of its development become an object for special studies of how modern developed countries manage to institutionalize and control socio-economic and political relations.

Developed countries (above all, EU member states) have committed themselves, together with all UN member states, to implement the Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development Agenda (Transformation of Our World).

With 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the world community has specific areas of activity to realize its ambitious vision of a peaceful, just, socially inclusive world that uses natural and human resources steadily, makes complex changes are needed at the economic, integrated, social (including educational and scientific) and environmental levels to ensure overall respect for rights and opportunities human, equality and self-determination. In addition to encouraging people and protecting the environment and social development, Member States have declared their determination to “take bold and transformative steps that must be urgently put in the path of sustainable development and resilience and promised to act together” and thus not give up. Thus, the concept of “partnership in the spirit of global solidarity” plays an important role in the implementation of the Agenda for 2030.

Collaboration at all levels is critical to sustainable development. Governments and civil societies, the private sector, the education sector and individuals must make every effort to get joint progress in the world. The United Nations has adopted the relevant General Assembly Resolution, Transforming Our World: A 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

Education as a key area and direction of sustainable development. Education is one of the key prerequisites for the implementation of the whole 2030 Program, so education plays a key role in the vision of a justice, peaceful and sustainable global society. The world community has set its own goal: “To provide inclusive, fair and quality learning and to promote all lifelong learning opportunities”.

To this end, all education partners worldwide must be involved. In particular, the objective of 4 “High quality education” is to achieve the following objectives:

- By 2030, create tools and models that will allow everyone to receive and complete free, fair and quality primary, secondary and higher education that will lead to relevant and effective learning and social development outcomes.
- Ensure access to quality education for all at all levels, creating the right conditions by 2030, enabling them to successfully advance to the next educational levels and provide lifelong learning.
- Allow all women and men equal and open access to high quality vocational and academic education by 2030.
- By 2030, make sure that a significantly greater number of young people and adults acquire the knowledge, skills and competencies associated with employment or self-employment.
- Eliminate gender differences at all levels of education by 2030 and ensure equal access to all levels of education for all, including people with disabilities, indigenous peoples and children with disabilities.
- Ensure adequate literacy and skills by 2030 for all adolescents and the vast majority of adults.
- Ensure that by 2030 all students will acquire the knowledge and skills needed for sustainable development, including through education for sustainable development, sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promoting a culture of peace and non-violence, through global civic education and recognition cultural diversity and the contribution of culture to sustainable development.

This is first and foremost an analysis of global institutional, ideological and social

transformations, the functioning of ideology, the system of education and mass communication, methods of limiting social struggle within the framework of a formalized social system, and above all within the framework of the development of existing public institutions and, in particular, market control. Modern science finds the presence in the modern society of social states and forces, that are alien to human and not only failed to weaken, but more than that – today, human being and humanity have fallen into such rigid dependencies and dangers that do not simply threaten to turn them into an object of their subordinated social relationships, but also jeopardize the very foundations of human life on a global scale. These problems can only be solved globally.

It seems possible to note that the modern industrial society, in spite of the high level of technological development, is in a latent form quite unfair and inhumane, since this society forms the so-called “one-dimensional people”, puppet people, whose thoughts and behavior are easy to manipulate. Modern “late capitalist” society, manipulating public and individual consciousness, becomes a repressive tool for oppressing human freedom. This is even more true for societies of the “early capitalist” and “transit” types, where the repressive tools are explicit and violence is not hidden and is the main method of social management.

At the same time, mental alienation is directly related to social estrangement, with economic fetishism, which turns a person into a certain commodity function. Modern society puts on a straitjacket of repression for every person, starting from one’s birth. In conditions of total alienation, oppression of man by the impersonal forces of power someone might look like a schizophrenic just because he/she is simply not able to carry out his normal reactions in order to adapt to an abnormal society in which he/she constantly faces conflicting anonymous relations of hierarchy, domination and subordination at the level of both society and family. In the context of our current comprehensive insanity of the state and society, everything that we call norm, health, freedom, all of our points of reference is doubtful and ambiguous. A person who says that he/she has lost his/her soul looks like crazy. A person who claims to be an inferior race representative can be quite respected. The individual is not able to find creative inspiration in the field of culture, since it has taken the form of a commercial enterprise, in the understanding of which human life and the needs of the individual must be fabricated like goods for a profitable sale.

Giving away its energy and most of the time in the activities of institutions alienated from the person, the modern personality loses the family from which its real purpose is emasculated, loses the reality of communication and friendship relations and, most importantly, loses the ability to creative imagination and activity, – modernizing oneself as the production force of a mass technological-commercialized society instead. The main values of this type of society, which at the same time are effective levers of social management, are rational hierarchical discipline and irrationalized mass consumption (as the main form of interpersonal relations). In the new economy, wealth is determined by the possession of humane capital – knowledge has become not only an independent factor in production, but also a major factor in the whole system of factors. The formation of a new economy is the result of the development of new knowledge. Estimates show that doubling of knowledge occurs every decade. This is due to the fact that they, in the form of information as systematic data, are changing the appearance of the modern world at an increasing rate.

There is a need not only to improve the institutional level of the global society, but also to implement a radical restructuring of thinking, development and implementation of new approaches, organizational forms and methods of shaping strategies for its development.

The concept of globalization becomes basic – from it the processes of social transformation and institutionalization, and more precisely, transformational institutionalization, are emerging.

Globalization is a dual-transformational phenomenon, since its inception it has been in the state of so-called dynamic equilibrium, i.e. constantly accompanied by equal and equally significant phenomena – evolution, progress and revolution (social, economic, production, political, legal, scientific, technical, political, legal, state and ideological, etc.) on the one hand and regression, devolution – on the other. However, it is very revolution (world-class revolutionary transformations) that is both a condition and a dialectical state of globalization.

Therefore, this process (globalization) takes place simultaneously in the forms of integration, unification, internationalization, expansion, as well as – regionalization, deglobalization, alter-globalization and so on.

Co-Authors

Additional Information

Links

There are no links for this session available.

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